

How to Cite (APA): Erdogan Akbulut, H. & Atmaca, H. E. (2025). Predicting the triage level and clinical outcome of emergency department patients using machine learning approaches. In Proceedings of the IMSS'25 (pp. 63–71). Düzce University - Türkiye, 25–27 September 2025.

Predicting the triage level and clinical outcome of emergency department patients using machine learning approaches

Hatice Erdoğan Akbulut¹ and H. Ediz Atmaca²

¹ Department of Industrial Engineering, Antalya Bilim University, Antalya, Türkiye
hatice.erdogan@antalya.edu.tr

² Department of Industrial Engineering, Gazi University, Ankara Türkiye
hediz@gazi.edu.tr

KEYWORDS - triage level prediction, clinical outcome prediction, machine learning, hyperparameter optimization.

ABSTRACT

Emergency departments are critical units where fast and accurate decisions must be made within the healthcare system. In emergency departments, where the density is usually high, incoming patients are evaluated and examined according to their urgency levels by passing through the triage area for prioritization purposes. In recent years, has been conducted for predicting patient triage levels to help triage professionals. Predicting patients' clinical outcomes is another common topic in the literature when looking at the prediction studies done with triage data. In this context, an application was made within the scope of the study aiming to estimate both the triage levels and the clinical outcomes of patients applying to the emergency department. In the study, the MIMIC-IV-ED dataset used in the literature was utilized. In the data pre-processing stage, text-based expressions were converted into numerical form with natural language processing methods. Then prediction models were created using random forest, XGBoost, and MLP algorithms. Finally, the performances of these algorithms were presented comparatively.

1 INTRODUCTION

The emergency department is considered the most critical unit of a hospital due to its complexity and variability. [1]. To manage this complexity in hospitals, patients attending the emergency department are prioritised. This process is usually carried out by triage nurses in the triage areas of hospitals. Triage is a clinical risk management system designed to safely regulate patient flow in cases where clinical need exceeds the current capacity of emergency services around the world. [2].

Information collected from patients in the triage fields is used not only to guide patients according to the triage levels, but also for other purposes. At the same time, the clinical outcome of this information is one of the subjects studied. The clinical outcome is a concept that describes the patient's situation at the end of the emergency service process after admission to the emergency department. These results include being discharged from the emergency department and returning home, being transferred to an intensive care unit, being hospitalised, or dying in the emergency room

within a certain period. All these cases are considered clinical outcomes that determine the patient's final disposition from the emergency department.

The aim of this study is to estimate the triage level and clinical outcomes using the MIMIC-IV-ED dataset. During the pre-processing phase, TF-IDF was used to convert text variables into numerical form. During the estimation phase, the Random Forest (RF), XGBoost, and Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) algorithms were used, and hyperparameter adjustment was performed using the GridSearchCV technique. The results are presented comparatively using different performance metrics.

The rest of this paper is organised as follows: Section 2 covers the literature review. Section 3 introduces the dataset and its pre-processing. Section 4 presents the application and Section 5 includes the results and suggestions.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

The purpose and methods used in prediction studies conducted with data obtained during and after triage were investigated within the scope of the study. Figure 1 uses the PRISMA 2020 flow diagram to present the method followed in the research conducted in the ScienceDirect and PubMed databases using the keywords '*emergency department*' and '*triage prediction*'. The focus of our examination was studies that were published in 2020 and later.

Figure 1: Literature screening process flowchart

As a result of the examinations, eight studies were included in the study and the details of these studies were presented. Additionally, Table 1 presents the machine learning approaches and prediction objectives made in the studies.

Yun et al. [3] aimed to predict which patients would require critical care using XGBoost and deep neural network algorithms. They compared the performance of these models with that of the initial model prepared using the KTAS system and observed that the XGBoost model performed better. Sax et al. [4] aimed to predict hospitalization and fast-track suitability of patients. For this purpose, they used MLP and LSTM methods and obtained an AUROC value of 0.87 for both purposes with the dataset they included triage nurse's notes. Elhaj et al. [5] aimed to predict clinical outcomes for patients using triage data. They classified clinical outcomes as critical or non-critical and tried nine different machine learning algorithms to predict these outcomes. The random forest algorithm produced the best results across all performance metrics. Araouchi and Adda [6] created a stacking model using SVM, GBM and LR models to estimate triage levels, achieving the best success rate with this model compared to six others. El Menyar [7] used various machine learning algorithms to predict triage level, mortality, and the activation of the massive transfusion protocol. They reported that RF performed best. Gan et al. [8] used machine learning algorithms to identify triage indicators for critically ill patients presenting with acute abdominal pain, ensuring that diagnostic and treatment resources were immediately available. Following estimation studies on their two-level triage system (urgent and non-urgent), the ANN algorithm was found to be the most effective. Shen et al. [9] developed knowledge-based large language models to support decisions on patient triage. They introduced the Sequential Domain-Task Adaptation framework and conducted experiments on the MIETIC dataset using various large language models. Fine-tuned models achieved high accuracy rates, particularly for high-risk patients. Halwani et al. [10] used machine learning models to predict triage levels in the KTAS system, reporting that Gaussian Naive Bayes followed by SVM, RF and LightGBM models performed well.

Table 1 Summary of studies using various ML models and prediction made

Authors (year)	Prediction made	Using ML Method(s)
Yun et al. [3]	Clinical outcome (ICU)	XGBoost, DNN
Sax et al. [4]	Clinical outcome (hospitalization) Fast-track eligibility	MLP LSTM
Elhaj et al. [5]	Clinical outcome (discharge, ICU admission, hospitalization, COVID-19 services, mortality)	LR, DT, KNN, SVM, MLP, GBM, XGBoost, AdaBoost, and RF
Araouchi and Adda [6]	Triage level	SVM, RF, ANN, GBM, LR, XGBoost, Stacking model (SVM, GBM, LR)
El-Menyar et al. [7]	Triage level Clinical outcome (mortality) Massive transfusion protocol activation	KNN, LR, DT, SVM, RF, XGBoost, ANN
Gan et al. [8]	Triage level	LR, KNN, SVM, ANN, XGBoost, DT, RF
Shen et al. [9]	Triage level	LLM's
Halwani et al. [10]	Triage level	KNN, SVM, DT, RF, GNB, LightGBM

KNN: K-Nearest Neighbours, LR: Logistic Regression, DNN: Deep Neural Network, MLP: Multi-layer Perceptron, DT: Decision Tree, ANN: Artificial Neural Network, LLM's: Large Language Models, XGBoost: Extreme Gradient Boosting, RF: Random Forest, GNB: Gaussian Naïve Bayes, LightGBM: Light Gradient Boosting Machine, SVM: Support Vector Machine, GBM: Gradient Boosting Machine.

In studies, not only the triage level of patients but also the clinical outcomes are among the purposes of estimating with triage data. In general, it is emphasized that random forest, XGBoost and neural network models are more successful. In the scope of the study, random forest, XGBoost, and MLP methods from artificial neural networks were used.

3 MIMIC-IV-ED DATASET AND PREPROCESSING

The MIMIC-IV-ED dataset comprises emergency department admissions at Beth Israel Deaconess Medical Center between 2011 and 2019. [11]. The data set consists of six tables: ed_stay, diagnosis, medrecon, pyxis, triage and vitalsign. The database contains data from 425,087 emergency department visits. The study used a data set obtained by combining the "ed_stay" table, created to monitor emergency department admission and discharge processes, and the "triage" table, which contains triage data. Each patient has a subject_id, and a stay_id that represents their arrival at the emergency department. In addition to basic information such as the patient's gender, race, arrival transport and disposition, the vital signs taken in the triage unit are also included. These vital signs include body temperature, heartrate, oxygen saturation (o2sat), systolic blood pressure (sbp), diastolic blood pressure (dbp), pain level, triage level and chief complaint.

The following steps were performed during the preprocessing phase of the dataset:

- Data for numeric variables, such as temperature, heart rate, respiratory rate, o2sat, sbp, dbp were filtered according to the normal value ranges specified by Tsoni et al. [12]. Patient records that fell outside these ranges were removed from the dataset.
- The race variable was reclassified into the following categories: 'ASIAN,' 'BLACK,' 'HISPANIC,' 'WHITE,' and 'OTHER.'
- The 'LEFT WITHOUT BEING SEEN,' 'ELOPED,' 'LEFT AGAINST MEDICAL ADVICE,' 'EXPIRED,' and 'OTHER' categories in the disposition variable were combined under 'OTHER.' The variable was then restructured into four main categories: 'HOME,' 'ADMITTED,' 'TRANSFER,' and 'OTHER.'
- Several inconsistencies were identified in the pain variable, which should have values between 0 and 10. For values indicating ranges, such as "3-5" and "4/6," the average of the two numbers was taken. Additional characters (e.g., "+," "-") adjacent to numerical values were removed. Numbers expressed in words (e.g., "five") were converted to the corresponding digits. Values above 10 and non-standard textual expressions were removed from the data set.
- A comprehensive cleaning and standardization process was implemented for the textual variable "chief complaint." All text was converted to lowercase. Special characters and punctuation were removed. Variations such as "with" and "w/" were replaced with commas. Abbreviations were converted to standard form for consistency. Ordering expressions (e.g., "first," "1st," etc.) were removed. Expressions indicating the day, month, year, duration or frequency (e.g., "for three days" or "yesterday" or "month" or "x 2 weeks" or "x 1 month" or x2) were removed. Directional terms ("r", "l", "bilateral") were removed, and multiple complaints written together were separated appropriately. Finally, the data set was cleaned by removing all empty cells containing patient data.

Following the relevant pre-processing steps, approximately 370 000 patient records were obtained for use in the analysis. The 'chief complaint' variable, a text-based variable, was quantified using the TF-IDF (Term Frequency – Inverse Document Frequency) method, a natural language processing technique. TF-IDF is a statistical technique that calculates the importance of a word in a specific document relative to all documents. Consequently, the maximum number of features (max_features) was determined to be 250, and the prediction models were trained with this value. The descriptive statistics of the final data set obtained are presented in Table 2.

Table 2 Statistical overview of the dataset

Numerical variables	Range	Median
temperature	(56-111.4)	98
heartrate	(13-250)	84
resprate	(1-97)	18
o2sat	(8-100)	99
sbp	(5-299)	133
dbp	(0-297)	77
pain	(0-10)	4
Categorical variables	Count (n)	Frequency (%)
gender		
FEMALE	202041	54.71
MALE	167264	45.29
race		
WHITE	214705	58.14
BLACK	82714	22.40
HISPANIC	30492	8.26
OTHER	25636	6.94
ASIAN	15758	4.27
arrival transport		
WALK IN	233608	63.26
AMBULANCE	124267	33.65
UNKNOWN	10262	2.78
OTHER	1107	0.30
HELICOPTER	61	0.02
Text variable	Count (n)	Frequency (%)
Chief complaint (the top 5 complaints)		
abd pain	35890	9.72
Chest pain	27559	7.46
transfer	18867	5.11
nausea	18630	5.04
s/p fall	17901	4.85
Target variables	Count (n)	Frequency (%)
acuity (ESI) – triage level		
1	11341	3.07
2	120778	32.70
3	209140	56.63
4	27045	7.32
5	1001	0.27
disposition -clinical outcome		
HOME	219867	59.54
ADMITTED	128338	34.75
TRANSFER	5909	1.60
OTHER (LEFT WITHOUT BEING SEEN, ELOPED, LEFT AGAINST MEDICAL ADVICE, EXPIRED)	15191	4.11

4 APPLICATION

A significant class imbalance was observed in the triage level and clinical outcome variables. Initially, hyperparameter optimization was performed to improve the performance of the models. In this context, hyperparameter values tried in each model are presented in Table 3 for both triage level and prediction of clinical outcomes. The hyperparameter optimization process was carried out by using the GridSearchCV method in the Scikit-learn library with 5-fold cross-validation on the training data. Hyperparameter optimization was executed in accordance with the ‘accuracy’ metric.

Hyperparameter values are based on the default settings in the Scikit-learn library and studies on hyperparameter adjustments have been taken into consideration in the literature to try appropriate values and intervals to the problem. Probst et al. [13] for Random Forest algorithm, Lima Marinho et al.[14] for XGBoost algorithm, Valarmathi and Sheela [15] for both XGBoost and Random Forest, and Shekhar et al. [16] for MLP has been used. The parameter values of the models that provide the best estimates for triage level and clinical outcome are given in Table 4. When Table 4 is examined, it is seen that the best hyperparameter values used in the models for predicting triage level and clinical outcome are largely similar.

Table 3 The set of hyperparameters for each selected model

Model	Parameter	Values
Random Forest	n_estimators	[100, 300, 500, 1000]
	max_dept	[4, 6, 8, 10]
	max_features	['sqrt', 'log2']
	criterion	Gini, Entropy
	min_sample_leaf	[1, 3, 5]
	min_samples_split	[2, 5, 7, 10]
	XGBoost	n_estimators
	max_dept	[3, 5, 8]
	learning_rate	[0.01, 0.1, 0.2]
	subsample	[0.7, 0.9]
	colsample_bytree	[0.7, 0.9]
MLP	hidden_layer_sizes	(50,), (100,), (50, 50)
	alpha	[0.0001, 0.001, 0.01]
	activation	['relu', 'tanh']
	solver	['adam', 'sgd']
		learning_rate_init

Table 4 Hyperparameters of models providing the best predictive performance for triage level and clinical outcome.

Model	Parameter	Best hyperparameter values for triage level prediction	Best hyperparameter values for clinical outcome prediction
Random Forest	n_estimators	300	300
	max_dept	10	10
	max_features	'sqrt'	'sqrt'
	criterion	Entropy	Entropy
	min_sample_leaf	1	1
	min_samples_split	2	10
XGBoost	n_estimators	1000	500
	max_dept	5	5
	learning_rate	0.1	0.2
	subsample	0.7	0.7
	colsample_bytree	0.7	0.7
MLP	hidden_layer_sizes	(50,50)	(100,)
	alpha	0.001	0.0001
	activation	'relu'	'relu'
	solver	'adam'	'adam'
	learning_rate	'constant'	'constant'

Table 5 Performance metrics of models

for Triage level					
Model	Accuracy	Balanced Accuracy	Recall	Precision	F1-score
Random Forest	0.65	0.28	0.65	0.62	0.59
XGBoost	0.71	0.45	0.71	0.70	0.70
MLP	0.71	0.42	0.71	0.70	0.69
for Clinical outcome					
Model	Accuracy	Balanced Accuracy	Recall	Precision	F1-score
Random Forest	0.70	0.35	0.70	0.70	0.66
XGBoost	0.74	0.47	0.74	0.73	0.73
MLP	0.74	0.46	0.74	0.73	0.72

When Table 5 is examined, the performances of the models for both prediction problems show similar trends. The XGBoost model demonstrated superior performance compared to other models in all performance metrics based on the triage level prediction results. The MLP model yielded results very close to those of the XGBoost model. In contrast, the Random Forest model performed poorly in the balanced accuracy metric. As seen in Table 2, this is due to a significant imbalance in the distribution of the ‘acuity’ and ‘disposition’ variables classes. This imbalance demonstrates that the Random Forest model is inadequate for handling imbalanced datasets.

5 CONCLUSION

In this study, triage level and clinical outcome prediction were performed using Random Forest, XGBoost, and MLP methods using MIMIC-IV-ED data set. The results obtained were presented as comparative. According to the results, XGBoost produced more balanced results, while Random Forest performed poorly in correctly predicting minority classes in unbalanced data sets.

In future studies, data augmentation, data reduction, or hybrid methods can be applied to solve data imbalance. Beyond traditional word embedding methods, it is recommended to use more advanced natural language processing techniques such as CBOW, ELMo, and BERT in the data preprocessing process. In addition, metaheuristic approaches such as genetic algorithms can be used to scan the search space more effectively in hyperparameter optimization. However, due to the text-based structure of the dataset, the application of deep learning-based models, which are more advanced forms of neural networks, has the potential to increase classification performance.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. S. Saoud, A. Boubetra, and S. Attia, "A simulation knowledge extraction-based decision support system for the healthcare emergency department," *Int. J. Healthcare Information Systems and Informatics*, vol. 11, pp. 19–37, 2016, doi: 10.4018/IJHISI.2016040102.
- [2] K. Mackway-Jones, J. Marsden, and J. Windle, *Emergency Triage: Manchester Triage Group*, 2nd ed. Hoboken, NJ, USA: John Wiley & Sons, 2013
- [3] H. Yun, J. Choi, and J. H. Park, "Prediction of critical care outcome for adult patients presenting to emergency department using initial triage information: An XGBoost algorithm analysis," *JMIR Medical Informatics*, vol. 9, p. e30770, 2021, doi: 10.2196/30770.
- [4] D. R. Sax, E. M. Warton, O. Sofrygin, D. G. Mark, D. W. Ballard, M. V. Kene, D. R. Vinson, and M. E. Reed, "Automated analysis of unstructured clinical assessments improves emergency department triage performance: A retrospective deep learning analysis," *J. Am. Coll. Emerg. Physicians Open*, vol. 4, 2023, doi: 10.1002/emp2.13003.
- [5] H. Elhaj, N. Achour, M. H. Tania, and K. Aciksari, "A comparative study of supervised machine learning approaches to predict patient triage outcomes in hospital emergency departments," *Array*, vol. 17, p. 100281, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.array.2023.100281.
- [6] Z. Araouchi and M. Adda, "TriageIntelli: AI-assisted multimodal triage system for health centers," *Procedia Computer Science*, vol. 251, pp. 430–437, 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.procs.2024.11.130.
- [7] A. El-Menyar, M. Naduvilekandy, M. Asim, S. Rizoli, and H. Al-Thani, "Machine learning models predict triage levels, massive transfusion protocol activation, and mortality in trauma utilizing patients’ hemodynamics on admission," *Computers in Biology and Medicine*, vol. 179, p. 108880, 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.combiomed.2024.108880.
- [8] T. Gan, X. Liu, R. Liu, J. Huang, D. Liu, W. Tu, J. Song, P. Cai, H. Shen, and W. Wang, "Machine learning-based prediction models for analyzing risk factors in patients with acute abdominal pain: A retrospective study," *Frontiers in Medicine*, vol. 11, 2024, doi: 10.3389/fmed.2024.1354925.

- [9] Q. Shen, X. Zhang, H. Ren, Q. Guo, and Z. Yi, "Knowledge-embedded large language models for emergency triage," *Knowledge-Based Systems*, vol. 318, p. 113431, 2025, doi: 10.1016/j.knosys.2025.113431.
- [10] M. A. Halwani, G. Merdad, M. Almasre, G. Doman, S. AlSharif, S. M. Alshiakh, D. Y. Mahboob, M. A. Halwani, N. A. Faqerah, and M. T. Mosuily, "Predicting triage of pediatric patients in the emergency department using machine learning approach," *Int. J. Emergency Medicine*, vol. 18, p. 51, 2025, doi: 10.1186/s12245-025-00861-z.
- [11] A. Johnson, L. Bulgarelli, T. Pollard, L. A. Celi, R. Mark, and S. Horng, "MIMIC-IV-ED (version 2.2)," *PhysioNet*, 2023, doi: 10.13026/5ntk-km72.
- [12] R. Tsoni, V. Kaldis, I. Kapogianni, A. Sakagianni, G. Feretzakis, and V. S. Verykios, "A machine learning pipeline using KNIME to predict hospital admission in the MIMIC-IV database," in *Proc. 14th Int. Conf. Information, Intelligence, Systems & Applications (IISA)*, IEEE, 2023, pp. 1–6, doi: 10.1109/IISA59645.2023.10345903.
- [13] P. Probst, M. N. Wright, and A. Boulesteix, "Hyperparameters and tuning strategies for random forest," *WIREs Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery*, vol. 9, 2019, doi: 10.1002/widm.1301.
- [14] T. L. Marinho, D. C. do Nascimento, and B. A. Pimentel, "Optimization on selecting XGBoost hyperparameters using meta-learning," *Expert Systems*, vol. 41, 2024, doi: 10.1111/exsy.13611.
- [15] R. Valarmathi and T. Sheela, "Heart disease prediction using hyper parameter optimization (HPO) tuning," *Biomedical Signal Processing and Control*, vol. 70, p. 103033, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.bspc.2021.103033.
- [16] S. Shekhar, A. Bansode, and A. Salim, "A comparative study of hyper-parameter optimization tools," in *Proc. IEEE Asia-Pacific Conf. Computer Science and Data Engineering (CSDE)*, IEEE, 2021, pp. 1–6, doi: 10.1109/CSDE53843.2021.9718485.